

Influence of Supervision of Instruction ... (Maigari, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15079913>

Influence of Supervision of Instruction on Teachers’-Classroom-Productivity and Students’ Academic-Achievement among Secondary Schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council

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Abstract

The study was carried out to investigate the perceived influence of supervision of classroom instruction on teachers' classroom performance and students' academic achievement in senior secondary school in Abuja Municipal Area Council. The purpose of the study was to find out the perceived influence of supervision of instruction on teachers' classroom productivity and students' achievement. One research questions and one corresponding null hypothesis guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 80 senior secondary school teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Abuja, with a sample size of 66 teachers selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. A 5-item structured question was the instrument for data collection. tagged "Supervision of Instruction and Teachers productivity Questionnaire" (SITPQ)). A test – retest method was used for reliability of the instrument at 0.05% level significant. The research questions were answered using mean scores and standard deviation. The findings revealed, among others, that supervision of instruction enable teachers to discover new abilities and qualities in teaching; that supervision of instruction enhances the provision of adequate instructional materials, teachers' productivity and students' academic achievement. Based on the findings the researcher concluded conferences and seminars organized by instructional supervisor's influence teachers' classroom productivity also to a great extent. and recommended, among others, that supervision should be carried out regularly, that more supervisors should be appointed, and that teachers should see supervisors as mentors.

Keyword: Teachers' Productivity, Supervision of Instruction, Classroom, Students Performance.

Introduction

Supervision of instructional is a continuous process that aims at improving teaching by providing needed services to teachers. Improving teaching is a complex process in which many elements should intermingle. Teachers are at the center of this enhancement process, their acceptance of instructional supervision and interaction with instructional supervisors provide the catalyst for any supervisory achievement. Supervision has its origin from the Latin word "Super video" meaning "to oversee" (Adenaike and Adebajo, 2016). Therefore, "Supervision can be seen as a way of advising, guiding, refreshing, cheering, stimulating, improving and administration certain groups with the hope of persuading people to desist from applying wrong procedures in carrying out certain functions on their jobs and at the same time try to emphasize the importance of good human relations in an organization". The traditional approach of supervision is a fault-finding approach, the supervisor goes to school to criticize and condemn teachers, not seeing anything good in them (Adenokun, 2011). Educational supervision is the process or act of seeing to it that the policies, principles and methods established for achieving the objectives of education are properly and successfully carried out (Akilajia, 2014). This process involves using expert knowledge and experience to oversee, evaluate and cooperatively improve the conditions and methods of doing things connected with the teaching-learning problems in schools. The need to supervise the instructional process cannot be over emphasized; hence Ezeocha (2012) is of the view that most of the schools activities and all the school programmes require supervision. Supervision of instruction is a process of assisting the teachers to improve themselves and their instructional abilities so as to enhance effective teaching and learning (Akilajia, 2014).

It is a service rendered to teachers which is directed towards controlling the quality of their classroom instruction. Supervision of instruction aims at identifying areas of work that need to be improved upon. Oraemesi (2012) is of the opinion that supervision of instruction is important for a number of reasons. To him; "the supervisee learns during supervision, since the supervisor is more knowledgeable, he corrects and advises the supervisee. This is done through friendly interaction. It also enhances personal professional growth of the teacher since interaction and greater knowledge gained at supervision promotes personal growth". Education has been known to be the antidote to poverty and ignorance and the key for unlocking natural resources (Obaji, 2006). Since education is accepted to be an instrument

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of change; teachers serve as the main operators of the instrument while the students are referred to as the raw materials to be processed on which the change would be manifested over a period of time (Adenaike and Adebajo, 2016).

In an attempt to ensure that the value of education is being derived at all levels, some officials are charged with the responsibility to monitor the performances of all those who run education especially those in schools in order to find out or assess the extent of achievement of the goals of education. These officials are the ones officially designated as supervisors. Consequently, due to high cost of education, stakeholders are becoming increasingly interested in the school system. They monitor the teachers and their wards' activities critically to ensure that adequate teaching and learning activities take place. Thus Parents Teachers Association monitors the activities within the school and constitutes part of the team involved directly in supervision. The school is an organization where the generality of the citizens have input and support. As a result, the whole society and designated supervisors are in the position to help improve the system generally (Barr 2011). The process of supervision is complex and it permeates the whole structure of the school system. There seems to be little or no area of operation within the school where the need for supervision would not arise, although this may be in diverse proportions. As Udoh, Akpa and Gaug (2014) opined, the crucial areas within the school system that require supervision are instructional and discipline areas where both the content, method or mode of delivery.

Supervision is one of the oldest form of educational leadership, its position is still one of the most controversial to the extent of it being used interchangeably with inspection especially in Nigeria. The implication is that most people still apply the principles of inspection as perceived during the colonial and early part of the postcolonial Nigeria. This has not improved instructional services nor has it led to professional growth of teachers, because it does not encourage collegiality or collegueship. Another problem of supervision of instruction in schools is the inadequacy of supervisory personnel. Ogbonnaya (2015) said there is insufficient number of supervisors in most states of Nigeria. He maintained that insufficient number of supervisory personnel has militated against effective supervision of instruction in secondary schools as the few available ones are unable to reach out to all the schools as expected within the supervisory period.

Another problem is lack of proper training of the supervisors. As recognized by Oraemesi (2012) and Ogbonnaya (2015), both shared the opinion that administrators of education in Nigeria do not consider proper training of supervisory staff to carry out supervisory services. Ogbonnaya maintained that the criteria for appointing supervisors are basically the possession of a first degree in education and some years of teaching experiences. He reiterated that some supervisors are also appointed simply because "they know some officers at the headquarters" this leads to the placement of "wrong pegs in right holes".

Educations have a set of aims and objectives to achieve, these aims and objectives of education are achieved through the process of teaching and learning. The attainments of these educational goals are learning outcomes. These learning outcomes can be seen as academic achievement. Learning outcomes has been variedly referred to in literature as academic achievement, Students' academic achievement tends to indicate their level of effectiveness, resourcefulness, ability and throughput both in current and future times (Ewumi, 2009). While stressing on students' academic achievement in the educational system, opined that academic achievement of students particularly at the technical college's level is not only a pointer to the effectiveness of schools but a main determinant of the future of youths in general.

Students' academic achievement shows the success of an educational endeavor, students' achievement appears to be the main vital factor by which the effectiveness and attainment of any process of teaching and learning can be judged, academic achievement is a fundamental criterion by which all teaching and learning activities are measured (Aremu, 2007). The measure for assessing students' level of academic achievement is through achievement tests, examinations, and observations (Ernest-Ehibudu & Oporum, 2013). Major goal of the school is to work towards attainment of academic excellence by students and school may have other marginal objectives; emphasis is always placed on the achievement of sound scholarship. Students' achievement tends to be the gauge of school productivity (Gurr, 2014). Almost all educational stakeholders place high value on academic achievement and thus excellent academic achievement of children is often the expectation of parents and other educational stake holders Alaka and Obadara, (2013). Possibly, this explains the purpose of academics, have been putting up efforts to find ways of enhancing students' academic achievements.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study was to find out influence of supervision on instruction of teacher's productivity and student' achievement in senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. Specifically seek to find out:

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1. To determine the Influence of effective supervision of classroom instruction on teachers’ productivity and students’ academic achievement among public senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Research Questions

The following research question guided this study:

1. What is the Influence of effective supervision of classroom instruction on in teachers’ productivity and students’ academic achievement among senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05% level of significance.

Ho₁ There is no significant difference between supervision of classroom instruction on teachers’ productivity and students’ academic Achievement among senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council.

Methodology

The design of the study was survey research design, The population of the study included all the teachers in the four senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council. Source: Statistical Division, Ministry of Education November 2024. And students results of the senior secondary in Abuja Municipal Area Council Sample and Sampling Technique A total of 66 samples (33 female teachers and 33 male teachers from 4 Senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council) was used for the study. Simple random sampling technique to select samples from the population of teachers. The justification for this sample size is for the researcher to be able to get a more reliable and accurate data. Questionnaire and students results (achievement) was the instruments for data collection. The instrument was titled “Influence of Effective Supervision of Instruction on Teachers’ Productivity Questionnaire (ISITPQ)” Analysis In analyzing the data, the researcher used mean and standard deviation to analyze research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance The data analysis was done with reference to the one research question formulated to guide the study. The data was presented in tabular form showing percentage mean and standard deviation of the research question.

Presentation of Result

Research Question One

What is the Influence of effective supervision of classroom instruction on in teachers’ productivity and students’ academic achievement among senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the influence of effective supervision of classroom instruction on in teachers’ productivity and students’ academic achievement among senior secondary schools in Abuja municipal area council

S/N	Item	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
1	Interacting with a supervisor improve the productivity of the teachers.	66	3.21	0.79	Accepted
2	Interaction with supervisor scares some teachers.	66	1.76	0.93	Not Accepted
3	Interaction with supervisor makes teachers to look for more information on teaching subject(s).	66	3.24	0.79	Accepted
4	Interaction with my supervisor changes the attitude of teachers towards classroom instruction.	66	2.88	0.98	Accepted
5	Interaction with supervisor makes teachers discover new abilities and qualities for teaching and learning activities	66	3.31	0.81	Accepted

Source: Survey field work, 2024

In table 1, item 1 shows a mean of 3.21 (which falls between 2.50 and 3.49) and has a standard deviation of 0.79. Therefore, the decision level shows that the respondents to a great extent like Interacting with a supervisor improve the productivity of the teachers. Therefore, this item can be accepted. On the other hand, item 2 shows a mean of 1.76 (which falls between 1.50 and 2.49) and a standard deviation of 0.93. Therefore, the decision level shows that the respondents are of the opinion that

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Interaction with supervisor scares some teachers. So the item cannot be accepted because its mean falls below the criterion mean of 2.50. Item 3, depicts a mean of 3.24 (which falls between 2.50 and 3.49) and a standard deviation of 0.79. Therefore, the decision level shows that the respondents are of the opinion that Interaction with supervisor makes teachers to look for more information on teaching subject(s). Item 3 can therefore be accepted. Item 4 also shows a mean of 2.88 (which falls between 2.50 and 3.49) and a standard deviation of 0.98. The decision level shows that the respondents are of the opinion that Interaction with my supervisor changes the attitude of teachers towards classroom instruction. Therefore, the item can be accepted. Item 5 also shows a mean of 3.31 (which falls between 2.50 and 3.49) and a standard deviation of 0.81. Therefore, the decision level shows that the respondents are of the opinion that Interaction with supervisor makes teachers discover new abilities and qualities for teaching and learning activities. So, this item can be accepted. Based on the decision levels of the items research question one can be accepted.

Discussions of Findings

Teachers' classroom productivity is influenced by interaction with instructional supervisors. One implication of this finding is that interaction between teachers and instructional supervisors improves teachers' class instruction (Ogbonnaya 2015). This obviously has implications for the teaching profession, the students, the instructional supervisors, the society, and the nation. First, it means teaching was interesting for teachers and the time for instructional supervision will not be a time to panic or fidget but a time to always anticipate for because of the gains of such interactions on their teaching performance. This was also having a great effect on students' class performance which will make them develop their society and the nation at the long run.

The instructional supervisors will devote more time to such interaction because of the great influence it has on class instruction. Teachers' classroom productivity is influenced by the use of instructional materials suggested by instructional supervisors. This finding also has an implication in that it will help the FCT Ministry of Education see the necessity of providing teachers with instructional materials suggested by instructional supervisors. This will to a large extent reduce rate of improvisation of instructional materials by teachers and this will make students be well processed outputs. Teachers' classroom productivity is influenced by conferences and seminars organized by instructional supervisors for teachers. The implication is that it will make FCT State Ministry of Education rise up to the task of providing enough funds to organize seminars and conferences by instructional supervisors for teachers. Hence, improve the educational system of FCT and the nations at large.

Conclusion

Interaction with instructional supervisors influences to a great extent teachers' class performance. Instructional materials suggested by instructional supervisors influence to a great extent teachers' classroom performance. And conferences and seminars organized by instructional supervisor's influence teachers' classroom productivity also to a great extent. There is no significant difference in the perception of teachers with less teaching experience and teachers with more teaching experience with regards to influence of supervision of instruction on their class performance.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study, the conclusion drawn and its educational implications, the following recommendations are made:

1. The instructional supervisors in public senior secondary in Amac general having realized that the perception of teachers as regards influence of interaction with instructional supervisors on teachers' class productivity is positive, they should make it a point of duty to interact well with their supervisees. The instructional supervisors should always make themselves available and approachable to teachers.
2. The Post Primary School Management Board in Amac should always sensitize all instructional supervisors that they should perform their duties as helpers to teachers and not critics. That they should always be ready to assist teachers improve their teaching skills through their teamwork with teachers
3. Federal Capital Territory School Board should recruit more trained and qualified instructional supervisors to meet up with the. So that the existing few qualified instructional supervisors will not be overworked which will result to futility on their part.
4. Conferences and seminars be organized by instructional supervisors from time to time to cater for the professional assistance needed by teachers. Also, the FCT Ministry of Education should always finance effectively these conferences and seminars, since teachers believe these solve their professional problems.

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